

Original Article

Power of Social Media Influencers on Consumer's Purchase Intention in Pakistan

Dr. Mohammad Ali¹, Athar Azeem Qureshi², Zia Ul Haq³, & Sana Farhad⁴¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, COMSATS University Islamabad, Abbottabad Campus, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.² Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, COMSATS University Islamabad, Abbottabad Campus, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.³ Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, COMSATS University Islamabad, Abbottabad Campus, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.⁴ Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, COMSATS University Islamabad, Abbottabad Campus, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.**JOURNAL OF
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Abstract

The advertising field is the first to explore social media influencers, especially for the purpose of generating buzz among younger demographics and increasing brands' visibility on these platforms. This study is designed to investigate the influence of social media influencers, primarily focusing on source credibility, source attractiveness, product match-up, and meaning transfer. Emotional attachment is proposed to mediate between both the exogenous and endogenous relationships. Data collection was designed using the convenience sampling method and the dataset of 489 respondents was then analysed using SmartPLS 4. Source credibility and product match-up are found to be supported while source attractiveness and meaning transfer were not supported. Mediating effects of emotional attachment are also investigated. Implications, limitations, and suggestion for recommended research are further discussed.

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Introduction

Marketing communication has seen the use of social media as one of the most effective ways of reaching out to the target group of people of all ages (Lou & Yuan, 2019). In the past few years, many people have attracted an outsized following on the social media platforms based on the number of followers (Hudders et al., 2021; Ahamat et al., 2017). These people have managed to establish a good online platform where they have written on personal blogs and moved to mainstream social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, Facebook and YouTube (Hudders et al., 2021). The extensive utilization of online platforms has significantly revolutionized communication landscapes, allowing regular individuals to gather large audiences and establish themselves as influencers who shape opinions and influence behaviors (Freberg et al., 2011). Social media features like live chats and comments allow consumers to communicate directly with their favorite companies, influencers, and other users (Vrontis et al., 2021). Platforms like Instagram and YouTube have facilitated the rise of a new breed of internet celebrities with extensive reach and engagement among followers. Audiences perceive these emerging influencers more relatable and credible compared to traditional celebrities (Djafarova & Trofimenko, 2019). Social media users find expert influencers more compelling and genuine than celebrity endorsements on social media and in commercials (Borchers & Enke, 2022).

Recognizing their ability to connect with target demographics, especially younger cohorts, brands have increasingly collaborated with social media influencers for promotional campaigns. The global influencer marketing industry surpassed \$13.8 billion in 2021 and is deliberate to continue on a high progression trajectory as organizations further prioritize such partnerships in marketing strategies (Influencer Marketing Hub, 2022). Brands are increasingly establishing partnerships with digital influencers as they recognise the increasing

* **Corresponding Author:** Muhammad Ali | Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, COMSATS University Islamabad, Abbottabad Campus, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

✉ m.ali@cuiatd.edu.pk

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potential to communicate with their desired audiences, and influencers are rapidly becoming an indispensable element of their marketing strategies (Qalati et al., 2021). While influencer marketing initially concentrated in Western regions, emerging Asian markets are beginning to follow suit as social media proliferation expands in these countries. Pakistan represents a fascinating case study as digital transformation has accelerated tremendously in recent years. Internet penetration crossed 90 million users in 2021, with social media penetration at 43% expected to reach 55% by 2025 (DataReportal, 2022).

Influencer marketing has been the subject of an increasing amount of research in recent years (Reinikainen et al., 2020). Moreover, an in-depth review of the extant literature on influencer marketing demonstrates that researchers have carried out empirical investigations on the impact of social media influencers' attributes on purchase intention (Trivedi, 2018), customer engagement (Joyce, 2024), brand equity (Jun & Yi, 2020), and the development of brand loyalty (Pinto & Paramita, 2021). In recent years, digital platforms TikTok, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube have become increasingly integrated into the daily lives of individuals, particularly younger generations. This youth-led online ecosystem has bred a thriving community of popular bloggers, YouTubers, and celebrities wielding extensive influence. Brand sponsorships of social media influencers enable advertisers to authentically resonate with younger demographics where traditional media falls short (Si, 2015). Social media influencers has the ability to establish connections with customers, making them reliable, credible, and expert compared to the advertising method of celebrity endorsements (Berger et al., 2016) particularly, for brands aiming to attract a younger audience. Moreover, digital influencers are seen as being more credible when it comes to promoting and showcasing sponsored items (Tapinfluence, 2017).

Most studies have emphasized on conventional celebrity endorsements while this new internet famous endorsers has not been explored extensively. Celebrities and influencers also have dissimilarities in other aspects such as similarity and approaches with their followers that can significantly power the results (Jin et al., 2019). The importance of comprehending how digital influencers' communication behaviors impact their audiences' buying intentions has been emphasized in previous research (Hudders et al., 2021; Weismueller, 2020). How influencers affect users' mindsets and actions across various social media sites remains primarily unexplored (Martins et al., 2019; Chetioui et al., 2020; Sokolova & Kefi, 2020).

In addition, Syed Asim Shah et al. (2023) targeted only the Instagram users; therefore, there is a dearth of literature regarding the impression of other active platforms like TikTok and Facebook. Since each of the mentioned platforms is different and targets various audiences, it is crucial to understand how influencer marketing works in such social media contexts. Moreover, it is essential to examine the moderating role of user's emotional attachment to the influencers on the influence of the former on the latter on purchase intentions. There is limited knowledge in previous literature on how the development of emotions with influencers that may lead to a purchase can be effected. These gaps are addressed in this study by examining the effects of credibility, attractiveness, product match-up and meaning transfer on purchase intention with emotional attachment as the moderator. Platforms to be covered in the research will be TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram, particularly in Pakistani settings.

The present research proposes to investigate empirically the consumer responses to the concept of influencer marketing in the context of Pakistan's peculiar, youth-oriented social media environment. More precisely, it analyses how the perceptions of credibility, attractiveness, relevance, and meaning transfer influence the affective connection and the purchasing behaviour regarding the endorsed brands. Theory of Social Learning (Bandura, 1977) and Attachment Theory (Bowlby, 1982) can be used to hypothesise that promotional influencer attributes lead to emotional attachment and purchase intention. The data would be collected through surveys from the users of social media platforms including Instagram, TikTok, and Facebook in Pakistan, and will be analyzed by applying structural equation modeling version 4.

Theoretical Framework

This study focuses on the impact of social media influencers (SMIs) on the purchase intention of the consumer in the Pakistani context in line with the Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) and Attachment Theory (Bowlby, 1982). In the social learning theory, new behaviour is learned through observation of others in a given environment. This process consists of four essential sub-functions: attention, retention, reproduction and motivation. Regarding influencer marketing, followers actively monitor the brands that influencers promote and consume. They orient themselves to these behaviors, store them for later use as valid attitudes, and are driven to

replicate these behaviors based on perceived worth and functionality. Lou and Yuan (2019), Winter, Brückner, and Krämer (2021), and Liu et al. (2022) used Social Learning Theory to study Social Media Marketing influencer imitation. Therefore, social learning theory is well-suited for examining the attributes of social media influencers (such as credibility, attractiveness, and product match-up, and meaning transfer) in product endorsement and purchase intention.

Attachment Theory states that emotional attachment is a unique and significant fitting together between a person and a target. Emotional attachment is formed gradually as individuals go through various experiences. It involves a number of emotions and affections that can impact one's judgments, decisions, and purchasing behavior. In the context of SMIs, consumers build emotional attachments through repeated interactions and the personal connections influencers establish with their audience. This emotional attachment mediates influencer attributes (credibility, attractiveness, product match-up, and meaning transfer) and purchase intention. Others (Lou (2022), Shin, Pang, and Kim (2023), and Li and Peng (2020) have examined how emotional attachment affects influencer marketing.

Thus, we utilize social learning theory and attachment theory to analyze the Pakistani social media context. It examines how source credibility, source attractiveness, product match-up, and meaning transfer influence online purchase intentions with mediation effect of emotional attachment.

Hypotheses Development and Research Model

Source Credibility, Emotional Attachment, and Online Purchase Intention

The concept of source credibility, initially introduced by Hovland and Weiss in 1951, has been extensively studied in the realm of persuasive communication. Source credibility plays a significant role in how persuasive a message is perceived to be. It is determined by the perceived expertise and trustworthiness of the information source (Hovland et al., 1953). This approach has proven critical in understanding how media personas' features impact the success of their messages (Ecker & Antonio, 2021; Ismagilova et al., 2020).

Prior investigations have proven the significance of the SMIs credibility in shaping how the followers perceive them and consequently, their attitudes towards making a purchase (Ismagilova et al., 2020; Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019; Jamil & Hassan, 2014). Prior research has primarily centred on celebrity endorsements while the number of articles exploring the effect of SMI credibility on consumers' behaviours has risen recently (Yuan & Lou, 2020). Chaiken in a research done in 1980 was able to determine that for a source to be reliable the information that the source provides has to be considered truthful. One of the most significant criteria that can be applied to the evaluation of sources is credibility. There are two important factors: The first is the aspect of expertise and the second is credibility (Hovland et al., 1953; Muda & Hamzah, 2021; Özbölük & Akdoğan, 2022). Proficiency is the source's information and the degree of the source's familiarity with the field of interest (Ismagilova et al., 2020; Xiao et al., 2018), while trustworthiness is the perceived reliability of the source and its honesty in presenting information (Jin et al., 2019; Whitehead, 1968).

Therefore, in influencer marketing, the credibility of an influencer is still a determining element. This means that an influencer's suggestions will be beneficial based on their followers' view of their competence and genuine purpose. Hence, a follower's emotional attachment to an influencer, boosted by the influencer's trustworthiness and dependability, might result in purchase intention (Ecker & Antonio, 2021; Ismagilova et al., 2020). Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1a. Source credibility positively influences purchase intention.

H1b. Source credibility positively influences emotional attachment.

Source Attractiveness, Emotional Attachment, and Online Purchase Intention

The attractiveness model holds the opinion that physical attributes of the person transmitting a message has significant part in determining its efficiency. For instance, the acceptability of an advertisement enhances through the identification process particularly through the physical attractiveness of an endorser (Stefan, 2009). This model proves that commercial success is contingent upon the endorser in terms of similarity, liking, and familiarity with the consumer (Cialdini, 2007).

Cialdini (2007) also postulated that people are more responsive to individuals who have similar views or beliefs, personality, origin, or lifestyle to theirs, as these findings confirm. This principle is especially important for the different target audience and when a large number of goods or services is presented (Shimp, 2003). The

findings of the recent studies in influencer marketing align with these findings, with attractiveness and perceived similarity of SMIs positively influencing followers' emotional attachment (Ecker & Antonio, 2021; Ismagilova et al., 2020). Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H2a. Source attractiveness positively influences purchase intention.

H2b. Source attractiveness positively influences emotional attachment.

Product Match Up, Emotional Attachment, and Online Purchase Intention

The Product Match-up model states that the endorser and the product that they endorse should be as closely related as possible to allow the highest amount of marketing success. Mowen et al., (1979) have proposed that the effectiveness of an endorsement is a function of the balance between the endorser, the target audience, and the product as perceived by balance theory. According to the model, the affective relationship between these elements will improve the endorsement's effect, guaranteeing a high return on marketing investments.

The existing literature extends the logic of similarity and likability between the endorser and the product that enhances identification and interpersonal attraction (Braunstein & Zhang, 2005). Such alignment leads to a higher level of consumers' emotional connection, thus a higher purchase intention (Ecker & Antonio, 2021; Ismagilova et al., 2020). For social media influencers, it's crucial that their persona and the marketed product be consistent with one another, as this will increase the impact of the influencer. This in return make the endorsement more effective and assist in developing a deeper feeling with the followers. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H3a. Product influencer match up positively influences purchase intention.

H3b. Product influencer match up positively influences emotional attachment.

Meaning Transfer, Emotional Attachment, and Online Purchase Intention

Meaning transfer model by McCracken's (1989) explores the process through which cultural meanings are transferred from the cultural realm to consumer brands via opinion leaders, ultimately shaping consumers' self-concepts. This model conceptualizes endorsement as a process of meaning-movement, rather than mere persuasive communication. Influencers, by virtue of their persona and lifestyle, transfer symbolic meanings onto the brands they endorse, thereby creating specific brand image associations. It highlights how influencers imbue brands with cultural and aspirational meanings that resonate with their followers. Perceived congruence among the influencer's persona and the brand's principles is crucial to the success of this transfer. When individuals view a close connection between an influencer's personality and a brand's characteristics, they are more inclined to incorporate these associations into their own self-image. This process enhances emotional attachment and influences purchase intentions (Ismagilova et al., 2020; Ecker & Antonio, 2021). The symbolic value associated with endorsed products fosters a deeper connection with the brand, making the endorsement more impactful. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H4a. Influencer meaning transfer positively influences purchase intention.

H4b. Influencer meaning transfer positively influences emotional attachment

Emotional Attachment and Online Purchase Intention

A prior scholarly study shows that consumers build close emotional connections with influencers when they communicate candidly and personally (Sánchez-Fernández & Jiménez-Castillo, 2021; Ladhari et al., 2020). For example, Kowalczyk and Pounders (2016) emphasize the relationship that consumers build with celebrities and the products advertised on social networks and their purchasing behavior. Similarly, Rios Marques et al. (2020) demonstrate that influencers who effectively build personal relationships with their audience can significantly enhance brand attachment. This emotional attachment not only directly influences purchase intentions but also plays mediating role between influencer attributes and purchase intentions. Burnasheva and Suh (2022) found that emotional attachment mediates the relationship between celebrity credibility and consumers buying intention.

For instance, Dabija et al. (2019) argue that influencers who are physically attractive and perceived as genuine foster stronger emotional bonds, leading to increased purchase intentions. The effectiveness of endorsements is enhanced when the endorser and the product are compatible Mowen et al. (1979). This impact is mediated by the emotional connection that consumers have to the influencer and the brand. Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H5. Emotional attachment towards influencers positively influences the online purchase intentions.

Emotional Attachment as a Mediator

According to attachment theory, when a person develops a deep emotional connection to anything, they are said to have an emotional attachment (Bowlby, 1982). Attachment is defined by Bowlby (1969, p. 194) as a "lasting psychological connectedness between human beings," characterized by an innate need for closeness and intimacy with the object of attachment. This connection, formed over time via repeated encounters and experiences, has a major impact on individual judgments, decisions, and purchase behaviors (Bagozzi et al., 1999).

In social media marketing context, emotional attachment extends to relationships with social media influencers. Previous research highlights that consumers often build strong emotional connections with influencers who engage authentically and personally (Ladhari et al., 2020; Sánchez-Fernández & Jiménez-Castillo, 2021). Rios Marques et al. (2020) assert that influencers who effectively establish personal relationships with their audience can enhance brand attachment. Kowalczyk & Pounders (2016) found that young consumers frequently interact with celebrities and endorsed products on social media, which fosters a sense of connection that impacts their purchasing behavior.

Perceived emotional attachment is one of the most important factors that can be used to control many variables and customer purchase intention. Burnasheva and Suh (2022) proved that celebrity endorsement credibility has a moderating impact on the extent of the emotional connection that in turn influences the purchase intention. This means that credibility of social media influencers influences purchase intentions through emotion. In the same way, it was found that emotional attachment moderates the relationship between source attractiveness, source trustworthiness, product-match up and meaning transfer and purchase intention.

According to Dabija et al., (2019), the influencers that are viewed as being authentic and alluring cultivate build stronger emotional bonds and this leads to higher purchase intentions. Mowen et al. (1979) have proved that endorsements are more effective if the endorser and the endorsed product are related.

Figure 1

Research Model

Methods

Measures, Research Context, Participants and Procedure

All the independent variables including the mediator, emotional attachment, purchase intention, source credibility, source attractiveness, product match-up and meaning transfer were captured using the 5-point Likert scale. The reliability of the source credibility ($\alpha=0.905$) and source attractiveness ($\alpha=0.936$) of the study was determined by the work of Ohanian (1990). The product match-up measure ($\alpha=0.759$) was also derived from Ohanian (1990). The investigation conducted by Goldsmith et al. (2000) was the source of the measurements for meaning transfer ($\alpha=0.854$). Finally, Kumar's (2010) study was used to derive the measure for purchase intention ($\alpha=0.940$), while Thomson (2006)'s scale was employed to measure emotional attachment ($\alpha=0.836$).

According to the State Bank of Pakistan (2018), a significant amount of Pakistani firms are currently active on social media sites like Instagram and Facebook. Companies in Pakistan's cosmetics, jewelry, and clothing sectors engage with customers, advertise their products, and promote social commerce using social media

(Godey et al., 2016). Today's fashion industry is characterized by a dynamic and rapidly changing landscape. Consumers are becoming more knowledgeable, and there is a growing number of distribution and communication channels, such as social media and the internet (Helal et al., 2018). Adapting to these shifts would require fashion industry executives to foresee how consumers will act in these new contexts, a relatively new phenomenon in Pakistan and many other developing nations (Bon, 2015; Pakistan Advertisers Society, 2015). Consequently, this study delves into the Pakistani apparel, cosmetics, and jewelry industries to examine how emotional attachment influences social media purchase intentions. It also explores the relationship between influencer attributes (such as source credibility, source attractiveness, product match-up, and meaning transfer) and purchase intention. (DataReportal,2023) estimates that there are around 71.70 million people in Pakistan who utilize social media platforms for their daily lives. The sample for the research consisted of people who use social media and have a favorite influencer that they follow on Facebook, Instagram, and Tiktok. These people were included in the study. The recruitment of respondents was carried out using convenience sampling, which is in line with previous research that has investigated consumer behavior in the fashion sector (for example, Chang & Fan, 2017).

The data was collected between January and June of 2024. In order to verify that respondents were social media fashion consumers, they were asked a Yes/No screening question: "Do you use social media to purchase fashion products such as clothing, cosmetics, and jewelry, and do you have a favorite influencer that you follow on social media?" Individuals who responded with "No" were requested to remove themselves from the survey. The respondents were informed about social media influencers and were requested to provide their responses with their preferred social media influencer in mind. The survey was disseminated online to students enrolled in undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral programs at numerous institutions, utilizing Google Forms. University students were chosen due to their frequent purchases of fashion items through social media platforms and their substantial internet usage (Ashraf et al., 2014). Nevertheless, prior research has demonstrated that the generalizability of the results may be limited by the selection of university students (Knoll, 2015). Consequently, data were also collected from consumers employed in a variety of organizations. Out of the 700 surveys that were sent, 535 were returned, resulting in a 76% response rate and 489 usable questionnaires. The sample size of 489 was adequate for statistical analysis (Lou, C., & Yuan, S., 2019).

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

There was a balanced representation of the genders in the sample, with 54% female and 45% male, ensuring equal representation. Nearly half (48%) of those who took the survey were young adults (aged 18–25), with a third (34%) falling in the 25–30 age bracket. Nearly 52% of respondents were working adults, and more than 54% had bachelor's degrees. Forty percent also had master's degrees. When asked about their monthly income, 30% of respondents said it was between 50,000 and 100,000 Pakistani rupees. A whopping 49% of those who took the survey said they spend between one and four hours a day on social media.

Analytical Method and Data Analysis

To analyze the data that were obtained, we employed SmartPLS version 4 and IBM SPSS Statistics version 29. Due to the presence of measurement errors in the structural model, PLS analysis was employed because it correctly depicts the interrelation of all the latent variables (Farooq & Markovic, 2016).

Measurement models should be examined separately before the structural model analysis, as Hair et al. (2019) have advised. SmartPLS is an advanced software application for SEM analysis based on the PLS technique. SEM is a technique that is frequently employed by researchers in the social science to analyze data that is multivariate. Depending on the nature of the study, it is especially beneficial for analysing causal models that are based on theory. Hair et al. (2019) also highlight on the efficiency of SEM in this respect. Among the numerous procedures involved in SEM, there is one technique that is mainly aimed at estimating variance. In general, PLS is a technique of SEM that does not impose any constraints on the distribution of the data (Vinzi, et al., 2010).

Thus, it is perfect for use in many occasions due to its flexibility. However, if the predictors are nonparametric at any given time, then PLS is a variance-focused prediction-oriented technique. Hair et al. (2019) & Majchrzak et al. (2010) have pointed out that it is acceptable in terms of reliability in case of both small and big samples. Power analysis needs sample size of at least 30-100 instances with the suggestion depending on the model component with the greatest number of predictors (Ramayah et al. 2020). This ensures that as the sample

size increases, the parameters are always estimated and thus ensuring that the results will always be presented in the same format. Under situations where theory is scanty then PLS is useful because it deals with immense intricacy and provides high levels of predicted accuracy. The fact that PLS does not require precise specification of the model and it is less sensitive to assumptions about the distribution of the data makes it a more suitable option when the precise data distribution cannot be assumed. It has formative and reflective components in one model which make it easier to apply.

The first step was the factor analysis using SmartPLS to confirm the measurement model. This step made it possible to ensure that the measurement models were both reliable and valid before testing the structural model. Subsequently, path analysis was conducted to test the hypothesized relationships between the research constructs. Bootstrapping was used to check the significance of the path coefficients. Resampling technique, bootstrapping, helped to estimate the standard errors and confidence intervals with greater accuracy and increase the reliability of the results.

The research ensured that there was no common method bias before the measurement model was run. The variances are communicated by the measurement method rather than by the construct itself, as illustrated in this analysis. For this purpose, the procedures outlined by Podsakoff (2003) and the one-factor test developed by Harman (1976) were followed. To extract any hint of the presence of one of the factors from the factor analysis, we applied a principal component analysis with varimax rotation on all of the items of the measurement scale. According to the results obtained, the first factor explained 41 percent of the variance. It was found to be 50% of the total variation which is in line with the recommendation that it should not exceed 50%. According to Podsakoff et al., (2003).

Measurement Model Assessment

Reliability and Validity

Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability and average variance extracted (AVE) is used to establish the validity and reliability of the model. As shown in Table 1, the rho c, rho a, and Cronbach's alpha for attractiveness, credibility, emotional attachment, meaning transfer, product match up, and purchase intention are all higher than 0.700. These results suggest that the model's reliability level is acceptable (Hair et al., 2019). The average variance extracted values for attraction, credibility, emotional attachment, meaning transfer, product match up, and purchase intention are 0.785, 0.619, 0.632, 0.676, 0.516, and 0.728, respectively. Overall these values are high as all the convergent validity coefficients are more than 0.500 (Hair et al. 2019).

Table 1

Latent variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Attractiveness	0.936	0.940	0.936	0.785
Credibility	0.905	0.913	0.906	0.619
Emotional attachment	0.836	0.940	0.878	0.632
Meaning transfer	0.854	0.879	0.860	0.676
Product match up	0.759	0.765	0.761	0.516
Purchase intention	0.940	0.946	0.941	0.728

Table 2

Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Latent variable	Attractiveness	Credibility	Emotional attachment	Meaning transfer	Product match up	Purchase intention
Attractiveness	0.886					
Credibility	0.749	0.787				
Emotional attachment	0.536	0.624	0.795			
Meaning transfer	0.485	0.657	0.360	0.822		
Product match up	0.587	0.705	0.595	0.394	0.719	
Purchase intention	0.607	0.698	0.854	0.416	0.704	0.853

It has been established that the use of HTMT ratio is better when the discriminant is tested for reliability. As can be observed from Table 3, all the HTMT ratios are less than 0.9 to be precise, which is quite high discriminant reliability as according to Henseler et al., (2016).

Discriminant Reliability

To ensure that discriminant validity is present, Fornell-Larcker criteria are used, and it is confirmed. The purpose of this is to check the discriminant validity of each of the latent variables with the other constructs which is an important way of ensuring that they are indeed different (Hair et al., 2019). To determine the Fornell-Larcker criteria, the diagonal and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of the construct is presented in bold font as shown in the Fornell-Criteria Larcker’s correlation matrix provided below. On the other hand, the other values are linked to other variables and thus, it is not uncommon to find that they have association with other variables. The discriminant validity should be supported by showing that the AVE of each construct, which is highlighted in the diagonal, is greater than the associations of a given construct with all other constructs. It has been noted that all diagonal values are greater than their corresponding non-diagonal counterparts. Consequently, the discriminant validity of the framework is satisfactory.

Table 3
Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Ratio

Latent variable	Attractiveness	Credibility	Emotional attachment	Meaning transfer	Product match up	Purchase intention
Attractiveness	0.763					
Credibility	0.541	0.639				
Emotional attachment	0.507	0.663	0.373			
Meaning transfer	0.585	0.708	0.623	0.387		
Product match up	0.613	0.707	0.874	0.423	0.707	
Purchase intention						0.730

Factor Loadings

Figure 2 displays the various latent variables and their respective factor loadings. The factor loadings of the construct indicators indicate the individual strengths of each indicator. In order for the application to be evaluated, the factor loading should be above 0.700. Every indicator for a single construction demonstrates a positive factor loading.

Figure 2
PLS Path Model

Table 4

R Square

Latent variable	R-square	R-square adjusted
Emotional attachment	0.444	0.440
Purchase intention	0.730	0.729

R Square

The values for the latent variables R square and Adjusted R square are shown in Table 4. As stated by Hair et al. (2016), the R2 statistic might have values that are regarded substantial (R=0.750), moderate (R=0.500), or weak (R=0.250), all of which are considered genuine. The coefficient of determination (R2 value) for emotional connection is fairly low, measuring 0.444. Conversely, the R2 value for purchase intention is relatively robust, measuring at 0.730.

Structural Model Assessment

Analyzing a model's significance and dependability is a common statistical practice known as bootstrapping. Researchers can assess the significance of a model by repeatedly sampling from the original dataset. The t-statistic value indicates the significance of the regression coefficients. Figure 3 reveals several significant relationships that are worth noting. The study revealed a noteworthy correlation between credibility and emotional attachment, with statistically significant results ($r = 0.290$, $t = 2.615$, $p < 0.05$). This data reveals that when individuals see social media influencers as more trustworthy, they form considerably greater attachments to them. Similarly, with a t-value of 2.587 ($p < 0.05$), it can be inferred that credibility significantly affects purchase intention at a level of 0.248. The mediator emotional attachment significantly influences purchase intention ($t = 58.775$, $p < 0.05$), indicating its importance in determining purchase decisions. There was a favorable effect on emotional attachment (0.316 , $t = 3.925$, $p < 0.05$) and purchase intention (0.271 , $t = 3.900$, $p < 0.05$) when there was a high match up between the influencer and product. Although not statistically significant, attractiveness positively affects emotional connection and purchasing intention. Emotional attachment correlation coefficient of 0.147 and a t-value of 1.829 ($p > 0.05$) indicates a modest impact. The correlation coefficient for purchase intention is 0.126, with a t-value of 1.836 ($p > 0.05$), evidenced

a lesser impact. The relationships of meaning transfer are not statistically significant. Emotional attachment has a correlation coefficient of -0.026 and a t-value of 0.501 ($p > 0.05$), whereas purchase intention has correlation coefficient of -0.022 , t-value of 0.500 ($p > 0.05$). These results suggest that meaning transfer does not have a significant impact on these outcomes.

The outcomes of this investigation emphasize the significance about credibility, emotional attachment, and product match-up in determining consumers' purchase intention. Attractiveness and meaning transfer, in contrast, have a smaller effect.

Figure 3

Structural Model

Mediation Analysis

The total indirect and specific indirect effects are selected for the mediation analysis. The repercussions are illustrated in Tables 5 and 6. Table 5 confirms Hypothesis 1a by showing a significant relationship between credibility and purchase intention (Original sample = 0.314, $t = 3.031$, $p < 0.05$). In the same vein, there is no significant correlation between purchase intention and attractiveness (Original sample = 0.099, $t = 1.406$, $p > 0.05$) or between purchase intention and meaning transfer (Original sample = -0.045, $t = 0.994$, $p > 0.05$). It suggests that H2a and H3a are not supported. Purchase intention has a significant relationship with meaning product match-up (Original sample = 0.246, $t = 3.28$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 5

Total Indirect Effects

Hypothesis	Relationship	Original sample	T statistics	P values	Decision
H1a	Credibility -> Purchase intention	0.314	3.031	0.002	Supported
H2a	Attractiveness -> Purchase intention	0.099	1.406	0.160	Not Supported
H3a	Meaning transfer -> Purchase intention	-0.045	0.994	0.320	Not Supported
H4a	Product match up -> Purchase intention	0.246	3.428	0.001	Supported

The findings in Table 6 suggest that emotional attachment (original sample = 0.314, $t = 3.031$, $p < 0.05$) significantly mediates the relationship between credibility and purchase intention, and h1b is supported.. Additionally, the results indicate that emotional attachment does not serve as a mediator in the relationship between purchase intention and attractiveness, as well as between product compatibility and purchase intention. Consequently, the data does not support the hypotheses H2b and H3b. The relationship between product match-up and purchase intention is significantly mediated by emotional attachment (original sample = 0.246, $t = 3.428$, $p < 0.05$). Consequently, the hypothesis H4b is supported.

Table 6

Specific Indirect Effects

Hypothesis	Relationship	Original sample	T statistics	P values	Decision
H1b	Credibility -> Emotional attachment -> Purchase intention	0.314	3.031	0.002	Supported
H2b	Attractiveness -> Emotional attachment -> Purchase intention	0.099	1.406	0.160	Not Supported
H3b	Meaning transfer -> Emotional attachment -> Purchase intention	-0.045	0.994	0.320	Not Supported
H4b	Product match up -> Purchase intention	0.246	3.428	0.001	Supported

Discussion

Utilizing attachment theory and social learning theory, this research examines how social media influencers impact Pakistani consumers' purchase intentions. The study was designed to examine the direct and indirect effects of various influencer attributes on purchase intentions, specifically through the mediating factor of emotional attachment. Social media marketing is a dynamic field that is constantly evolving, and researchers are constantly investigating strategies to improve consumer purchase intentions. This investigation emphasises the importance of source credibility, source attractiveness, product-influencer match-up, and meaning transmission in influencing purchasing behaviour through mediation of emotional attachment.

The findings validate the hypothesis that the influencer's credibility is positively significant on the level of emotional attachment (H1a) and purchase intention (H1b). The study reveals that there is a higher probability that consumers will buy products that are recommended by influencers they consider to be trustworthy. Since the emotional appeal is more personal in nature, trustworthiness and expertise of the source are particularly relevant

when it comes to strengthening the bond, which is likely to translate into positive purchase intentions. These findings support social learning theory according to which individuals tend to be influenced by people they see as credible (Bandura, 1977).

On the other hand, there are hypothesis H2a & H2b, which presuppose that influencer's attractiveness influences the level of emotional attachment and purchase intention; however, these hypotheses are not approved by the results of the present study. On its own, attractiveness captures attention but does not have any positive effect on purchase intentions or emotional attachment. This investigation implies that while physical attraction may grab the attention of the consumer, it must be supported by other attributes including credibility to influence the purchase intention. It is possible to state that the hypotheses connected with the product influencer match-up between the product and influencer (H3a and H3b) are also supported. This goes further to indicate that compatibility between the persona the influencer portrays and the product enhances both the emotional attachment and purchase intention. This makes the endorsement more appealing to the consumers, hence increasing its validity, and making it more convincing to the consumers. This finding shows that there is a need to ensure that one gets the right influencers that have a good image and personal attributes that are close to the brand and its products.

H4a and H4b, which posit that influencer meaning transfer affects positive emotional attachment and purchase intention, are refuted by the outcomes of this research. Lack of significant effects of the identified relationship implies that although influencers may link certain aspects of their personality to promoted products, this does not affect the consumers' actions. This discovery underlines the complexity of the consumer attitudes and behaviours implying that the such factors as credibility and product match up are far more influential than the brand personality.

The research results bear significant support to the last hypothesis; H5 which states that emotional attitude towards influencer has a positive impact on purchase intention. H2 confirms that all the influencer attributes have a direct and significant impact on the purchase intention of the consumers, and that this relationship is fully mediated by emotional attachment, thus underlining the importance of the emotional aspect in the consumers' decision-making process. This result is in consonance with attachment theory, where it is expected that people require meaningful relationships in improving their purchase intention.

Contributing to the existing body of literature, this study elucidates by presenting empirical data that supports the effects of influencer credibility and product match-up in altering the consumers' purchase intentions in a positive manner. This research adds to the existing literature regarding the part that emotional attachment takes in these relationships; better illustrating the manner in which social media influencers impact customer behavior. Furthermore, the research presented in the paper is novel in the sense that it focuses on the Pakistani context, which is still underrepresented in the literature. In doing so, it provides useful information for marketers who want to engage in influencer marketing in emergent markets in particular (Lou and Yuan 2019).

Theoretical Implications

The current study also fills a significant theoretical gap in the context of Pakistan by examining the role of social media influencers and emotional attachment in influencing purchase intentions. Based on the social learning theory and attachment theory, it explores how those characteristics of influencers, including credibility, attractiveness, product match-up, and meaning transmission, affect the consumers when it comes to social media marketing.

Firstly, this study highlights the relevance of source credibility in forming emotional attachment and enhancing purchase intention, as supported by the Social Learning theory. This underlines the importance of credible influencers in which affects consumer perception since credibility elicits positive emotions and leads to higher purchase intentions. This research builds on the existing literature, where the majority of the studies have investigated trust in more general context of online marketing (e. g. Yahia et al., 2018).

Secondly, the perceived attraction of influencers does not affect the consumers' emotional attachment or purchase intentions, which deviates from the expected result. Result means that even if attractiveness grabs the consumer's attention, it is not enough to provoke extra attention and make a difference in consumer's choice. This work improves upon current knowledge by arguing that additional factors play a larger role in consumers' decisions: the influencer's credibility, the congruency between the product and the influencer.

The positive relationship between product-influencer match-up and emotional attachment, as well as purchase intentions underscores the importance of match-up between the influencer and the product. It enhances the credibility of the endorsement, hence improving the customer interaction and buying behaviours. In line with and extending prior research, it emphasizes the necessity of choosing appropriate influencers for effective marketing strategies (Lou & Yuan, 2019).

In a similar manner, the research observed that meaning transfer originating from influencers to goods does not have an influence on the purchase intention/Emotional attachment. This proves that influencers can associate their personality to items but this does not necessarily translate to action. As such, by presenting a more nuanced conception of the boundary of meaning, the transfer in influencer marketing these findings address a gap in the knowledge.

From the study, a considerable positive relationship exists between purchase intentions and the level of emotional attachment, thus providing a supporting argument to the attachment theory, that emotional attachment is critical in the consumer decision-making process. The above analysis confirms the importance of the emotional attitude toward the product as a moderator between consumers' behaviour and influencers' characteristics. It means that in order to improve buying intentions, it is necessary to try to create some emotional bonds. This research is significant in the sense that it seeks to explain how various factors affect the consumers' behavioural pattern by integrating the concept of emotional attachment into the context of social media marketing.

Moreover, this research aims at filling the gap by providing an understanding of the Pakistani market and understanding of the consumer behavior in the light of the emerging market economy. Previous research has been mainly centred on markets within the western zones. However, this study brings a more profound insight by studying the processes within a different cultural and economic environment (Kapitan & Silvera, 2016).

Practical Implications

These findings come as insights for the retailers in Pakistan especially regarding the role of social media in improving the consumer purchase intention. Based on the current state of social media marketing of Pakistan and the challenges it is experiencing, there is vital importance that retailers need to establish trust and this can only come by partnering with influencers. The study focuses on the influencer credibility when it comes to emotional appeal and persuading the consumer. This means that retailers must concentrate on the types of influencers that are reliable and experts in their field.

This is in consonance with the study done by Lee and Eastin (2020) and also Erkan and Evans (2022) where they established that credibility has a strong influence on trust in influencer marketing. These levels of expertise help to build up emotional bonds and hence have a bearing on the probability of purchase. Thus, in the context of a conceptual model of emotional attachment and purchase intentions, the active combination of credibility, product match-up, attractiveness can be proposed. This approach can give better chances of success than other approaches. Lim et al., (2020) suggest that it is advisable for retailers to be selective when selecting the influencers with an attractive appearance but also with the right values as the brand as well as the merchandise promoted.

An important focus of the study is the close association between influencers and products which significantly contributes to the creation of the emotional attachment and the purchase intention. This is evidence why it is important to match the influencers and products according to the strategic plan. Surprisingly, the investigation reveals that the transfer of meaning from influencers to products does not influence the level of emotional attachment or purchase intention among consumers. The findings shown here reveal that while influencers have the capacity to impact the consumer behavior by their personal characteristics, it is insufficient to compel the consumers to act. In this context, credibility is something that retailers should give precedence to, over symbolism, which is associated with the influencer. In this regard, the finding is similar to the study done by Jin et al. (2019). The positive and strong relationship between perceived emotional attachment and purchase intentions underlines the importance of building emotional bonds between the brand and the customers. This is why it is necessary for the retailers to create the marketing strategies that would appeal to emotions and build closer connections with the brand among the consumers. Another strategy is to take advantage of storytelling,

behind the scenes content, as well as engaging activities in social media, which was presented by Miquel-Romero et al (2020).

Given the cultural context of the Pakistani consumers, which attaches great importance to social relations and recommendations from friends, retailers can easily apply strategies based on social proof and influence of peers in their marketing activities. Engaging happy customers to provide their positive testimonial (word of mouth) and recommendations on social media can go a long way in enhancing trust and influence the buying decision of consumers Huang and Benyoucef (2020). Social media should be managed with a focus on peer communications on the social networks by the retailers, while enabling and encouraging consumer engagement.

Retailers are encouraged to consider the incentive-seeking characteristics of Pakistani consumers in their operations. Researchers Ali et al. (2021) have identified that using incentives like monetary bonuses, discounts, and other special offers is an effective way of gaining attention and building trust. The incentives should be marketed well on the social media platforms through which retailers should embark on a massive campaign especially during the national and religious festivals which are major peak periods for fashion products. Using the contests and giving away products can help in the development of a close relationship between the consumers and the brand.

Consumers have to be empowered by supporting their opinions and making sure that their questions and comments are responded to as soon as possible and as genuinely as possible. Retailers should proactively interact with consumers on social media, demonstrating sincere interest in their suggestions and complaints, aligning with the recommendations proposed by Azhar and Abid (2021). This clear and honest communication cultivates a feeling of empowerment and trust, resulting in higher likelihood of making online purchases.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

Potential areas for further research to address include the study's weaknesses. This study's focus was exclusively on the fashion industry in Pakistan. Purchase behavior in social media settings can vary significantly, depending on the industry. Therefore, it would be advantageous for further investigation to replicate these findings across different industries, including electronics, sports, and tourism, to improve the overall applicability of the outcomes. A more comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior in social-mediated marketing environments will be achieved by examining these diverse contexts.

Research model in this study was tested using a cross-sectional survey. This method only shows the connections between variables at a single point in time; it can't track how they've changed. Influencers attributes, emotional attachment, and purchase intentions should be studied more thoroughly in future studies by using experimental methodologies or longitudinal designs. The development of these associations may be better understood via longitudinal studies, and the establishment of causal links can be better accomplished through experimental study.

In addition, Pakistan has a collectivist society, which provided a backdrop for the research. Nevertheless, it is imperative to recognize that cultural distinctions may influence consumer behavior; consequently, it is imperative to recognize that the findings of this investigation are unlikely to be generalizable. In order to comprehend the ways in which culture affects the connections between customer motivation, emotional attachment, and purchase intentions, subsequent studies should investigate the proposed model in other cultural contexts. Comparing various cultures may provide a broader look at how the results can be utilized internationally. Nevertheless, the study model can be extended further by considering the influence of other factors like perceived risk and customer commitment which may act as moderator variables. It is assumed that the knowledge of how perceived risk affects online transactions might be helpful in the process of building trust. Customer commitment on the other hand reveals the loyalty between customers and brands and its incorporation might enhance the explanatory power of the model.

In terms of future research, it would be reasonable to investigate how demographic factors, for example age, gender, and wealth may affect the first model connections. Demographic factors are therefore very important in determining customers' behaviour and attitude. It is possible that a better understanding of these key aspects will help organizations to craft precise marketing approaches.

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